

Low Dose Mifepristone in the Management of Uterine FibroidsNath Piyalee¹, Nath Pranoy², Thapa Pranjit³¹Post graduate Trainee, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Silchar Medical College, Silchar, Assam, India²Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Silchar Medical College, Silchar, Assam, India³Professor and HOD, Department of Radiology, Nagaon Medical College and Hospital, Nagaon, Assam, India

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Abstract**Background:** Uterine fibroids are the most common benign smooth muscle tumors of the female reproductive system. It accounts for one-third of all gynecological hospital admissions and is the most common indication (making up approximately 40%) for hysterectomy in premenopausal women. Mifepristone (RU 486) effectively reduces menorrhagia and other fibroid-related symptoms, and its size.**Objectives:** To study the effect of low dose Mifepristone for 3 months on improvement of fibroid related symptoms and its size.**Materials and Methods:** This was a hospital-based prospective cross-sectional study which was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology in Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam. 246 women were enrolled and divided into two groups. Patients in Group 1 received Tab Tranexamic acid (500 mg) and Tab Mefenamic acid (500 mg) thrice daily during menstrual bleeding for a period of 3 months. Patients in Group 2 received Tab Mifepristone 25 mg daily for 3 months.**Results:** Mean PBAC score reduced by 96.03%, Mean Numeric Pain Rating Scale Score for dysmenorrhea reduced by 82.87%, fibroid area reduced by 34% and hemoglobin concentration increased by 10% at 3 months in Group 2. These changes in Group 2 were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) compared to Group 1.**Conclusion:** Mifepristone has proven to be safe and effective as compared to treatment with tranexamic acid and mefenamic acid for management of uterine fibroids.**Keywords:** Fibroids, Mifepristone, Tranexamic acid, Mefenamic acid.

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Introduction

Uterine myomas or fibroids are the most common benign smooth muscle tumors of the female reproductive system. They are monoclonal tumors that originate from the myometrium. Their prevalence among women is generally cited as 10% to 20%, but it is as high as 70% to 80% in sonographic studies. [1] Numerous factors have been linked including age, heritage, race, body mass index, hypertension, endogenous hormonal factors, reproductive factors, infection, environmental factors, and lifestyle (smoking, alcohol consumption, diet, caffeine intake, stress and physical activity). [2] It accounts for one-third of all gynecological hospital admissions and is the most common indication (making up approximately 40%) for hysterectomy in premenopausal women. [3] It is predominantly an estrogen-dependent tumor. The majority of fibroids are usually asymptomatic (75%). Menstrual

abnormalities like menorrhagia (30%) is considered to be the typical symptom of symptomatic fibroid. This can lead to iron deficiency anemia. A sufficiently large uterus can lead to significant discomfort and other concerning clinical features like pelvic pain, abdominal distension, and chronic pressure symptoms such as increased urinary frequency. It may interfere with reproductive function by causing infertility or preterm births. [4] Malignant transformation in fibroids can occur in less than 0.1% of cases. Both medical and surgical methods are available for the management of fibroids. Several minimally invasive procedures like uterine artery embolization or laparoscopy can be performed to preserve the uterus. Medical management aids in reducing the symptoms and signs. [5] Clinical, biochemical, and pharmacological studies provide evidence that progesterone plays a significant role in the

pathogenesis of myomas. This led to the development of antiprogestins like Mifepristone as a therapeutic option for myomas.

Mifepristone (RU 486) is effective in reducing menorrhagia and fibroid size. It is synthesized from norethindrone and acts by competitively inhibiting the progesterone receptors. Its mechanism of action involves strongly binding to progesterone receptors in the endometrium, and weakly to estrogen receptors and also upregulation of androgen receptors. It causes delay or inhibition of ovulation and amenorrhea. [6] The side effects include endometrial hyperplasia [7], nausea, vomiting, elevated liver enzymes, pain abdomen, diarrhea, hot flushes, headache, and bodyaches. It has been reported that the use of Mifepristone for fibroids has circumvented the need for many invasive procedures. A significant reduction in fibroid size, uterovaginal bleeding and increase in blood hemoglobin have been achieved with the use of Mifepristone for fibroids. It has also been reported that the endometrial changes are reversible on treatment discontinuation.

Another alternative, Tranexamic acid and Mefenamic acid are routinely used medications requiring cyclical administration which can reduce Menstrual Blood Loss (MBL) by up to 50%. Oral tranexamic acid is an FDA-approved drug in the treatment of ovulatory AUB. Studies have shown that the use of tranexamic acid resulted in the significant reduction in blood loss, leading to improvement in the overall quality of life across various domains such as, work, social interaction, leisure, and physical activities.8

This study aimed to determine the effect of low dose Mifepristone for 3 months on fibroid-related symptoms, its size and evaluate the side effects of Mifepristone.

Methods and Methodology

This study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology in Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam over a period of one year starting from 1st June 2022 to 31st May 2023 after approval by the Institutional Ethical Committee.

Study Design: Hospital based prospective cross-sectional study.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated by the Daniel sample size formula [9]:

$$N = \{Z^2 \times p(1-p)/d^2\}$$

Where, N = Sample size

Z = Statistics for a level of confidence (1.96 for 95% confidence level)

p = expected prevalence or proportion (Prevalence of uterine fibroids in sonographic studies = 0.8) [2]

1-p = 0.2

d = precision (d is considered 0.05 for producing good precision and smaller error of estimate)

So, the sample size was calculated as 246. The study was conducted on 246 patients. Each patient was randomly placed in one of the two groups of 123 patients each.

Inclusion criteria

Women of reproductive age group (18-49 years) with

1. All symptomatic fibroids of different sizes and anatomical positions but less than 12 weeks size.
2. All asymptomatic fibroids of size 2.5cm or more detected on ultrasonography done for evaluation of other complaints but less than 12 weeks size.
3. Asymptomatic multiple fibroids of size 2.5 cm or more detected on sonography done for evaluation of other complaints but less than 12 weeks size.

Exclusion criteria

- a. Fibroid of more than 12 weeks size.
- b. Women desirous of pregnancy or currently pregnant
- c. Breastfeeding
- d. Menopausal women
- e. Hb < 6.0 g/dl
- f. Unexplained, abnormal vaginal bleeding
- g. Any liver, renal or respiratory disease, bleeding disorders, adrenal, thyroid or heart disease.
- h. Atypical endometrial hyperplasia
- i. Adnexal masses
- j. Suspected or diagnosed malignancy
- k. Genital infections or Pelvic inflammatory disease
- l. sickle cell anaemia
- m. Use of Oral/systemic corticosteroids, Hormones Danazol within 3 months.
- n. Any contraindications to Mifepristone

Patients were divided into two groups, Group 1 and Group 2. A detailed history and clinical examination was done in all patients. They also underwent investigations like hemoglobin percentage, peripheral blood film, coagulation profile, thyroid profile, liver function tests and renal function tests, pelvic and renal ultrasound, Pap smear, and endometrial biopsy in selected cases. The patients in Group 1 received Tablet Tranexamic acid (500 mg) and Tablet Mefenamic acid (500 mg) thrice daily during menstrual bleeding for a duration of 3 months. The patients in

Group 2 received Tab Mifepristone 25 mg daily for 3 months. To ensure consistency, we instructed all patients to start taking their medication from the first day of the menstrual cycle. All patients were followed up at the end of 3 months period.

The primary variables for efficacy were menstrual bleeding which was evaluated by PBAC score, and dysmenorrhea which was assessed by Numeric pain scale rating scores (NPSR). Secondary variables for efficacy were fibroid size reduction, calculated by multiplying the length and breadth of the fibroid as observed on ultrasound and increase in blood hemoglobin levels.

Statistical analysis

Microsoft Excel sheet and Independent 't' test were used to statistically analyse the results.

All quantitative variables are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results and Observations

The average age was around 35.85 ± 5.73 years in Group 2 while it was around 35.43 ± 5.73 years in Group 1. Approximately 58% in Group 1 and 56% in Group 2 were having intramural fibroids, 20% in Group 1 and 18% in Group 2 submucosal fibroids and 14% in Group 1 and 17% in Group 2 had subserosal fibroids.

In Group 1, 83.7% patients experienced menorrhagia as the primary symptom, compared to 87% in Group 2, as assessed by PBAC score. 86.1% of patients attained amenorrhea with Mifepristone, reducing their PBAC score to 'zero'. {Table 1} The mean reduction in

PBAC scores in Group 1 was approximately 17% while it was 96.03% in Group 2. {Table 4}

76.4% patients in Group 1 and 78% patients in Group 2 had dysmenorrhea, the severity of which

was scored as per the Numeric Pain Scale Rating score. The mean reduction of NPSR scores in Group 1 was 26.9% while it was 82.87% in Group 2. {Table 4}

At the start of the study, the mean area of fibroid in Group 2, as measured by transvaginal ultrasound was 20.44 ± 3.69 cm². After 3 months of treatment with Mifepristone, a significant reduction in fibroid area was noted ($p < 0.001$). The mean fibroid area at the end of 3 months of treatment was found to be 13.48 ± 4.89 cm². {Table 6} It was observed that the average reduction in fibroid area was 34.27% with intramural fibroid, 32.59% with submucosal fibroid and 34.50% in subserosal fibroids. This reduction in size was statistically significant compared to Group 1. {Table 7}

In Group 2, reduction in uterovaginal bleeding was observed and 86.1% patients attained amenorrhea along with overall improvement in health. The analysis showed that the rise in haemoglobin levels at the end of treatment course was statistically significant. The average percentage increase in hemoglobin was 2.4% in Group 1 and 10% in Group 2. {Table 4} It was also observed that the average endometrial thickness was 8.77 ± 1.19 mm after 3 months treatment course with Tab Mifepristone.

Moreover, the resumption of menstrual cycle in patients occurred after an average of 31.04 ± 3.103 days after completing the treatment course. Side-effects were observed in 28% patients in Group 2 with Mifepristone. 5 patients had derangement in liver function test. Additionally, 6 patients each reported minor side-effects like backache and hot flushes and 17 patients had nausea. But these side-effects were not very severe and did not have any significant affect the patients' quality of life. In 6 patients (5%), the symptoms reappeared following the completion of treatment, who had to undergo hysterectomy.

Table 1: No of patients who attained amenorrhoea after 3 months of treatment

Group	No. of patients attained amenorrhoea after 3 months of treatment	Percentage
Group 1	0	0
Group 2	106	86.1%

Table 2: Mean value with Standard Deviation of various parameters before treatment

Parameter	Mean value before treatment		P value
	Group 1	Group 2	
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	131.80 ± 41.48	141.14 ± 54.51	0.13 (not significant)
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	3.71 ± 2.23	4.03 ± 2.35	0.27 (not significant)
Fibroid area (cm ²)	20.39 ± 3.57 cm ²	20.44 ± 3.69 cm ²	0.9 (not significant)
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	9.89 ± 0.92 gm/dl	9.90 ± 0.94 gm/dl	0.9 (not significant)

Table 3: Showing changes in the mean values of various parameters at 3 months after treatment

Parameter	Mean value before treatment		Mean value after treatment	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	131.80 ± 41.48	141.14 ± 54.51	109.35 ± 30.01	5.60 ± 15.47
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	3.71 ± 2.23	4.03 ± 2.35	2.71 ± 1.70	0.69 ± 0.71
Fibroid area (cm ²)	20.39 ± 3.57 cm ²	20.44 ± 3.69 cm ²	20.18 ± 3.71 cm ²	13.48 ± 4.89 cm ²
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	9.89 ± 0.92 gm/dl	9.90 ± 0.94 gm/dl	10.14 ± 0.89 g/dl	11.00 ± 0.59 g/dl

Table 4: Effect on various parameters:

Parameter	At the end of 3 months	
	Group 1	Group 2
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	17% decrease	96.03% decrease
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	26.9% decrease	82.87% decrease
Fibroid area (cm ²)	1.02% decrease	34% decrease
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	2.4% increase	10% increase

Table 5: Showing change in various parameters at 3 months after treatment compared to before treatment in Group 1:

Parameter	Mean before treatment	Mean at 3 months after treatment	P value
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	131.80 ± 41.48	109.35 ± 30.01	< 0.001 (Significant)
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	3.71 ± 2.23	2.71 ± 1.70	< 0.001 (Significant)
Fibroid area (cm ²)	20.39 ± 3.57 cm ²	20.18 ± 3.71 cm ²	0.65 (Not significant)
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	9.89 ± 0.92 gm/dl	10.14 ± 0.89 g/dl	0.03 (Significant)

Table 6: Showing change in various parameters at 3 months after treatment compared to before treatment in Group 2

Parameter	Mean before treatment	Mean at 3 months after treatment	P value
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	141.14 ± 54.51	5.60 ± 15.47	<0.001 (Significant)
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	4.03 ± 2.35	0.69 ± 0.71	<0.001 (Significant)
Fibroid area (cm ²)	20.44 ± 3.69 cm ²	13.48 ± 4.89 cm ²	<0.001 (Significant)
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	9.90 ± 0.94 g/dl	11.00 ± 0.59 g/dl	<0.001 (Significant)

Table 7: Showing change in various parameters at the end of 3 months in Group 2 compared to Group 1

Parameter	Group 1	Group 2	P value
Menorrhagia (PBAC)	109.35 ± 30.01	5.60 ± 15.47	< 0.001 (Significant)
Dysmenorrhea (NPSR)	2.71 ± 1.70	0.69 ± 0.71	< 0.001 (Significant)
Fibroid area (cm ²)	20.18 ± 3.71 cm ²	13.48 ± 4.89 cm ²	< 0.001 (Significant)
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	10.14 ± 0.89 g/dl	11.00 ± 0.59 g/dl	< 0.001 (Significant)

Discussion

The mean reduction in PBAC scores in Group 2 treated with Mifepristone was 96.03% whereas the mean reduction of NPSR scores was 82.87% in the same. There was a 34% decrease in fibroid size and 10% rise in hemoglobin levels in Group 2 at the end of 3 months.

The treatment of fibroids varies from medical therapy to hysterectomy. This study delves into the use of Mifepristone for managing uterine myomas, highlighting its promising role in future as the drug of choice. The median age of patients in this study was 35 years, aligning with other studies. This shows that a significant fraction of pre-menopausal women require treatment for symptomatic fibroids. According to the study by Carbonell et al. [10], amenorrhoea was achieved by 90% women.

According to the study of Niger Med Journal 11 75% patient's attained amenorrhoea with Mifepristone 25 mg once daily for 6 months. 40–70% patients attained amenorrhoea with Mifepristone 5-10 mg for 12 months whereas 100% patients attained amenorrhoea with 100 mg Mifepristone daily. This study showed 96.03% reduction in PBAC score in Group 2 during three months of treatment with Mifepristone and 86.1% women in achieved amenorrhoea. Whereas, 17% reduction in the PBAC score was observed in Group 1 with tranexamic acid and mefenamic acid. The reduction in score in both groups was statistically significant (p-test < 0.001). There was a decrease of 82.87 % in the NPSR scores for dysmenorrhoea after 3 months of treatment. Study conducted by Anupama et al 12 showed 87.5% decrease in dysmenorrhoea scoring with a dose of 25

mg/day whereas Carbonell et al [10] showed 85.7 % decrease when 5 mg/day was used and 70 % when 2.5 mg/day was used. Seema Saharan et al [13] reported a decrease of 79 % with dose of 10 mg/day. In this study, a statistically significant decrease in size of fibroids was seen (average reduction in area for all fibroids was 34%; 34.27% in intramural, 34.5% in subserosal and 32.59% in sub-mucosal fibroids). The study from Niger Med Journal 2011 [12] showed 47% decrease in fibroid size. This was consistent with the findings by Kirsty et al. [14] where, a 50% size reduction was achieved with 5-10 mg Mifepristone once daily for 6 months.

In our study, prompt decrease in menorrhagia and overall improvement in health was observed. There was 10% increase in haemoglobin levels following 3 months of treatment in the Mifepristone group which was statistically significant. This increase is less compared to most other studies and similar to Engman et al [15]. There was 22.5% increase in endometrial thickness in the present study after 3 months of treatment with 25 mg/day of mifepristone. The unopposed estrogenic effect on endometrium has been implicated as the cause. In a study by Carbonell et al [10], 2.5mg and 5 mg groups showed 30.9 % and 32.3 % increase in endometrial thickness after treatment. Sikha Seth et al [7] with a 25 mg/day dose showed an increase of 51.9 % which is more than that of our study.

Conclusion

Mifepristone has demonstrated significant efficacy in treating myoma, with unparalleled patient satisfaction rates as evidenced by various global studies. The primary challenge now is to determine the optimal dosage, frequency, and duration of treatment to maximize patient adherence and satisfaction while minimizing adverse effects. Our research has shown a notable 86.1% rate of amenorrhea among participants during the treatment period, a statistically significant finding. Patients reported substantial improvements in symptoms and overall well-being. Additionally, a considerable decrease in fibroid size led to lower PBAC and NPSR scores after three months of therapy. A daily dose of 25 mg of Mifepristone has proven to be safe, effective, feasible, and well-tolerated, with high levels of patient satisfaction. Further multicentric randomized studies with extended follow-ups and a larger sample size are recommended to better define the treatment duration.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

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